

From Complexity to Clarity: Simplifying OpenStreetMap Data for Improved Active Transportation Analysis

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Active Transportation (AT) refers to self-propelled, human-powered travel modes like walking and cycling [1]. To effectively analyze AT in urban environments, the availability of accurate street network data is paramount. Detailed information on street layout, connectivity, and accessibility [2] is crucial for supporting the evaluation and understanding of walking and bicycling patterns. Combining this information with demographic and environmental factors such as population demographics, AT-related crashes, and land use not only informs infrastructure improvements but also guides strategy development [3]. Such strategies aim to enhance the safety, efficiency, and attractiveness of AT [4,5], thereby mitigating issues such as traffic congestion, obesity, and air pollution [6].

Street network data comes from various sources, each presenting challenges regarding accuracy and update frequency. OpenStreetMap (OSM) offers a comprehensive, open-source geospatial database that is continuously updated by a global community of contributors [7]. OSM's strengths lie in its detailed coverage of road networks, including pedestrian pathways and bicycle lanes, which are crucial for AT analysis [8]. However, utilizing OSM data for AT analysis involves several challenges. Firstly, the granularity of its network can complicate modeling AT users' movements at the street level. For instance, when assessing AT safety or developing a walkability index, the current data representativeness on OSM requires significant manipulation to mitigate bias. Furthermore, due to OSM's open-editing model, the standards for mapping elements are not consistently defined, leading to contentions and variations in data quality [9]. Contributors often map elements based on personal needs and knowledge, introducing inconsistencies in the dataset [10,11]. As a result, in some areas, all designated lanes for various users are meticulously mapped, while in others, only a single lane representing the presence of a street is depicted [12,13]. Additionally, there are instances where only lanes for motor vehicles are detailed, with scant attention paid to lanes catering to other user groups. These inconsistencies necessitate careful consideration and significant data processing when using OSM for AT analysis to ensure accuracy and reliability.

In this study, we propose an innovative solution to generate an axial network specifically designed for monitoring and analyzing AT users, using exclusively OSM data

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(<https://github.com/achic19/SOD>). Our approach simplifies the network while preserving its topology. We apply this solution across diverse spatial contexts, from straightforward geographic regions to complex urban environments. Furthermore, we implement our methodology in several cities worldwide – Turin (Italy), Tel Aviv (Israel), and San Francisco (United State) – each characterized by unique urban structures.

The preliminary tasks use OSMnx [4] to acquire OSM street network data, converting it into a graph while correcting topological errors. Then, the data is stored in a geodata table, including polyline geometry, names, and road types. Our algorithm filters out unsuitable roads, like motorways and trunk roads, and replaces roundabouts with their central points.

The network is then ready for the multilane detection algorithm. Polylines identified in a multilane scenario are aggregated into a centerline and added to the Simplified OSM Data (SOD) network. Other polylines are added to the SOD network, retaining their original geometry. A multilane scenario is identified when polylines share the same street name, have similar angles, and are close together. Polylines are grouped by street name, and azimuth (0° - 180°) narrows the angle range to ensure that parallel lines are considered parallel, regardless of orientation. The Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) clusters similarly angled polylines using a 10° radius and a minimum of two samples. Through sensitivity tests, we determined that a 10° threshold effectively includes nearly parallel polylines while excluding those that are significantly misaligned. Outliers with significantly different angles are excluded. The remaining clusters apply a right and left shifted buffer to each polyline. If two or more polylines in the same class overlap by at least 10% in the shifted buffer, they're classified as multilane, and the entire class is replaced with one or more centerlines. The 10% threshold balances sensitivity (detecting true parallel lines) and specificity by minimizing false positives from minor geometric variations, such as slight bends or irregularities.

The core idea behind creating a new centerline is to identify its start and end vertices and then add intermediate vertices to preserve the overall shape of multilane polylines. Overlapping buffers are merged into a single polygon, and the two polygon vertices that best define the original polylines are used to establish the new centerline's start and end. Intermediate vertices are then added at regular intervals to maintain the original polylines' orientation.

The simplification process introduces significant changes to the locations of many polylines, resulting in issues of continuity, topology, accuracy, and inconsistency in the SOD network. Most problems can be resolved using existing methods, but connecting roundabouts requires extra effort. This process has three steps: transforming the roundabout representation to a point, connecting nearby dead-end polylines, and linking polylines in proximity. Following these steps ensures proper continuity and maintains the network's topology.

The case study centered on Turin, Italy, simplified its street network to 10,535 polylines from an initial 55,104. This effort reduced the complexity of 459 streets, converting 155 roundabouts to single points. Despite some challenges near intersections, the final version preserved topology (see Figure 1).

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Figure 1. displays various urban configurations before (represented by the red network) and after (illustrated by the blue network) the simplification process. These configurations range from simpler layouts (Figure 1a to Figure 1c), where streets are represented with a single lane, to intermediate complexity (Figure 1d - Figure 1f) featuring streets with two lanes, and finally, more intricate arrangements (Figure 1g - Figure 1i).

For validation, 46 streets in Turin were reviewed, revealing a 63% success rate, 22% with minor flaws, and 9% with partial success. Issues such as threshold errors, external mapping inaccuracies, and ambiguous street configurations affected the results. Similar challenges were faced in Tel Aviv, Israel, where 82% of 22 test streets matched perfectly with the reference network. Yet, 9% had minor issues, and 5% achieved partial identification/success. In San Francisco, the results showed 85% accuracy with 20 streets evaluated. While most streets were correctly simplified, minor flaws were present in a few cases. Overall, the methodology successfully streamlined street networks, although it achieved varying rates of success across different cities.

Our study offers a robust methodology for generating axial networks for AT users using OSM data, balancing data simplification with topology preservation. Its successful application across diverse cities such as Turin, Tel Aviv, and San Francisco demonstrate its versatility and effectiveness in varied urban environments. The approach simplifies the complex urban network data, streamlining pedestrian and bicycle analysis while retaining essential details. This enables urban planners and policymakers to better monitor and understand AT patterns, leading to infrastructure improvements that support safer, more efficient, and environmentally friendly urban mobility.

Our research offers both scientific contributions and practical benefits. Scientifically, it has been applied to evaluate the built environment for pedestrian walkability using a spatial data clustering approach. Additionally, it has been utilized in research to evaluate safety and bike network connectivity, aiming to improve bicycle and pedestrian infrastructure in California cities. Practically, this work has been published on GitHub, making the code accessible to everyone for their specific needs and goals.

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